

Welcome from the CUSTODES team

Dear reader,

We're pleased to welcome you to the fourth edition of the CUSTODES newsletter. The first half of 2025 has been full of milestones for our project, from collaborative meetings and expert panels to major events on cybersecurity and the future of AI. This issue recaps these activities and highlights upcoming opportunities to get involved. Thank you for following our progress toward a more agile and trustworthy EU cybersecurity certification landscape.

Project updates & events

Third Plenary Meeting – 4 & 5 February 2025

The year kicked off with our third plenary meeting in Madrid. Over two days, partners reviewed progress, demonstrated prototypes of the **Dynamic Risk Assessment (DRA)** and **Composite Conformity Assessment Process (CCAP)** and discussed integration roadmaps and pilot preparations. Live demos highlighted user interaction flows and blockchain-based traceability mechanisms, setting the stage for our mid term review and upcoming pilot deployments.

Project updates & events

Guidance Board Kick Off – 5 February 2025

Immediately after the plenary, CUSTODES convened the first session of its Guidance Board. Experts from standardisation, industry, academia and SMEs, including **Tony Rutkowski**, **Elżbieta Andrukiewicz**, **Vasileios Mavroeidis**, **Marta Irene García Cid**, **Eduard Marín** and **Alexandru Gal** were engaged in discussions focused on adoption barriers, integration of static analysis tools and the use of open source vulnerability data.

Custodes Horizon Project at InCyber Lille 2025

www.redalertlabs.com

InCyber 2025 – 1 to 3 April 2025

At the **Forum InCyber Europe (FIC)** in Lille, France, the CUSTODES partner **Red Alert Labs** presented our project and engaged with stakeholders from across Europe's cybersecurity community. Highlighting CUSTODES' dynamic, agile and reusable certification approach for composite ICT products, services and processes.

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Project updates & events

AI & Security Webinar – 30 April 2025

The graphic for the AI & Security Webinar features a dark background with a QR code in the top right corner. The title "AI & Security Webinar" is at the top, followed by "Meet the Speakers". Below this, there are two rows of speaker portraits with their names and affiliations. The bottom of the graphic includes logos for partners like elasticsearch, Predict 6G, Harpocrates, Confidential6G, Rigorous, Faith, Custodes, and 6G Cloud. It also contains a "SAVE THE DATE" section with the date "April 30th" and time "13:00-17:00h".

AI & Security Webinar
Meet the Speakers

Prof. Nineta Polemi
University of Piraeus
CIO & Co-founder of Trustilio S.A.

David Eklund
RISE Research Institute
of Sweden

Fotis Foukalas
Cogmin

Apostolos Pyrgelis
RISE Research Institute
of Sweden

Shen Wang
Assistant Professor,
Academic Director of the ISL4S
School of Computer Science,
University College Dublin, Ireland

Madhusanka Lynage
Associate Professor / Adj. Astra Fellow
Director of NICTAR
School of Computer Science,
University College Dublin, Ireland

Anastasio Giannopoulos
FI

Merlijn Sebrecchts
IMEC and Ghent University

Antonio Skarmeta
University of Murcia, Spain

Jorge Bernal
University of Murcia, Spain

Sotirios Spantideas
FI

Dr. Nenad Gilgic
CIO of Zenira Lab.

elasticsearch Predict 6G Harpocrates Confidential6G Rigorous Faith CUSTODES 6G CLOUD

SAVE THE DATE DATE April 30th TIME 13:00-17:00h

Later that month, our partners supported an online webinar exploring the intersection of artificial intelligence and cybersecurity. Hosted by the **ELASTIC, PREDICT 6G, HARPOCRATES, CONFIDENTIAL6G and RIGOROUS** projects, and supported by **FAITH, CUSTODES** and **6G Cloud**, the event took place on 30 April. Topics included privacy preserving AI, resilient and predictive security for 6G networks and blockchain-enabled network management. **Trustilio**, a CUSTODES partner, gave a keynote on how AI driven systems can be securely certified and how emerging EU regulations impact trustworthiness.

CyberSecDome Cluster Synergies Webinar – 15 May 2025

The graphic for the CyberSecDome Cluster Synergies Webinar features a central image of hands holding colorful gears. The text on the left side of the graphic includes the event title, date, and the text "Organised by". The central image also contains logos for various projects like COcyber, PHOENIX, SecAwarenessTruss, SYNAPSE, CUSTODES, CONSOLE PROJECT, and CRACOWI.

CyberSecDome
Organised by

Cluster Synergies Webinar

Date
15 May 2025

CyberSecDome
COcyber COE Synapse
CONSOLE PROJECT
PHOENIX
CUSTODES
CRACOWI

On 15 May, CyberSecDome hosted a “cluster synergies” webinar that brought together several Horizon Europe projects (**COcyber, PHOENIX, SecAwarenessTruss, SYNAPSE, CUSTODES, CONSOLE, COevolution and CraCoWi**) to exchange insights and foster collaboration. Speakers emphasised the value of coordinated action and structured collaboration across the cybersecurity ecosystem, underscoring CUSTODES’ commitment to building synergies with fellow EU initiatives working on digital resilience and civil defence cooperation.

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Project updates & events

TEDxPatras Workshop – 17 May 2025

At TEDxPatras 2025 p-Net delivered an engaging workshop titled “Think Before You Click! To Hackers, the Easiest Target is You!”. Supported by the **CURIUM** and **SAND5G** projects alongside **CUSTODES**, the interactive session raised awareness about common online threats and practical cybersecurity tips. Participants also visited the workshop booth to learn more about our joint EU projects and pick up informative flyers.

CyberHOT 2025 Summer School – 26 to 30 May 2025

From 26 to 30 May the fifth **Cybersecurity Hands On Training (CyberHOT) Summer School** took place in Chania, Crete. This internationally recognised training initiative brings together cybersecurity professionals, researchers and practitioners to advance practical skills such as ethical hacking, risk management and incident response. CUSTODES represented by **Cyberalytics (Dr. A. Miaoudakis)** and **Trustilio (Professor N. Polemi)** contributed to the event’s programme by presenting our composite certification framework and discussing how agile certification can support secure **ICT ecosystems**.

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Project updates & events

IEEE ICE25 Conference – 16 to 19 June 2025

In June, our partner **DEKRA (Dr. Jasmin Ćosić)** presented a paper on automating cybersecurity certification of composite ICT systems at the IEEE ICE25 conference in Valencia. The research leverages semantic technologies and rule-based reasoning to make certification processes scalable, transparent and fully aligned with EU cybersecurity initiatives. DEKRA's participation reinforces the value of combining industry expertise with academic research and celebrates their long standing commitment to testing and certification.

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Upcoming activity

IOSEC 2025 event on 4 – 6 August 2025

Looking ahead, CUSTODES proudly supports the Workshop on Information and Operational Technology Security - **IOSEC 2025**, which will be held in Chania, Crete, Greece, alongside the prestigious IEEE Conference on Cyber Security and Resilience (CSR) 2025.

CUSTODES hands on workshop at Techritory 2025

We're excited to announce that CUSTODES will hold a hands-on workshop at the **Digitalization & Connectivity: Techritory 2025** forum in Riga. The session is tentatively scheduled for the afternoon of **23 October 2025** (after lunch) and will be organised by our partner **p-NET**.

Stay connected

Engage with us

Interested in collaborating with CUSTODES or joining our pilots and Guidance Board?

We'd love to hear from you!

Reach out via our project website or social media channels.

Thank you for reading and for your ongoing support.

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The Consortium

The project unites 16 partners from 11 countries: Sweden, Germany, France, Italy, Belgium, Ireland, Spain, Greece, Cyprus, Netherlands, Switzerland, encompassing the necessary expertise to successfully accomplish the project's ambitious goals.

Secure analytics for the interconnected world

KEY FACTS

Title:	A Certification approach for dynamic, agile and reUSable assessmentT fOr composite systems of ICT proDucts, servicEs, and processeS
Acronym:	CUSTODES
GA No:	101120684
Start:	October 2023
End:	30 September 2026
Topic:	HORIZON-CL3-2022-CS-01-04
Type of action:	Innovation Action (IA)

Follow Us

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